

The Effect of a Proposed Training Program on Improving the Muscle Strength of the Arms with the Upward Strike Skill and the Feet with the forward Strike Skill among Kickboxing Players

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Abstract:

Introduction: Kickboxing performance relies on forceful actions and repeated strikes, requiring optimum upper and lower limb strength. **Objectives:** To see whether a proposed strength-oriented training program affects sport-specific arm muscle strength as assessed through upward strike performance in kickboxing players and forward strike performance as secondary outcome. **Methods:** The research was done using a controlled pre–post study design at Tiger Kickboxing Academy (Zarqa, Jordan) between August 1, 2024 and November 30, 2024. Fourteen male kickboxing athletes (black belt; ≥ 18 years; $M=22.2$ years, $SD=4.5$ years) were allocated to an experimental ($n=7$) that performed the proposed program plus regular training or a control ($n=7$) group which continued regular training. Standardized sport-specific tests were done pre- and post-intervention to measure outcomes. Between-group differences at post-test were assessed through ANCOVA adjusting for baseline. **Results:** The performance of the upward strike improved in the experimental group (15.33 ± 2.45 to 18.51 ± 2.76) while not improving significantly in the control group (14.82 ± 2.12 to 15.22 ± 2.37); ANCOVA showed a

significant group effect ($F=22.54$, $p=0.001$). The experimental group exhibited improved forward strike performance from 19.54 ± 3.62 to 22.35 ± 3.33 . **Conclusion:** The training program for kickboxing athletes was helpful in improving sport-specific arm strength as observed. There is a need for larger clinical trials.

Keywords: kickboxing; resistance training; muscular strength; striking performance; ANCOVA

1. Introduction

Kickboxing is a high-intensity combat sport in which repeated punches and kicks are executed under substantial physiological stress. Recent competition data show near-maximal intensity and a major anaerobic contribution during bouts (1). Strength-oriented training is commonly used to enhance neuromuscular capacity, improve strike performance, and support injury-prevention strategies in combat sports (2). Intervention studies in kickboxing suggest that targeted conditioning programs can improve general and sport-specific physical fitness, including strength-related outcomes (3).

Modern sports training relies on a set of methods and techniques that aim to continuously and sustainably improve athletic performance by applying the latest scientific discoveries related to the sports field (4). Penichet-Tomas (5) confirmed that the training process focuses on integrating technology and scientific knowledge into the design of training programs to raise the level of performance and achieve the best results.

Muscular strength is considered as an important component of physical ability and can generate maximum effort by the muscles during a specific activity, as it plays a fundamental role in performing many sports activities (6). Grgic et al (7) explained that training to develop muscle strength often includes resistance exercises such as weightlifting or bodyweight exercises, which stimulate muscle growth and increase muscle endurance.

Physical fitness consists of several elements that must be practiced in order to achieve optimal physical fitness and to achieve an appropriate level of physical fitness to practice all types of sports and exercise. One of the most important elements of physical fitness is muscular strength. This element can be considered the most important element of all elements (8). Muscle strength is a key physical fitness component related to sports performance (9). The muscle's ability to excite the most muscle fibers to overcome multiple external resistors is called strength. This can also mean the maximum effort able to be produced to perform a muscular contraction (10). The muscle strength of the upper body is one of the basic elements of functional and athletic physical performance (10). The muscles of the upper body include the muscles of the chest, shoulders, arms, and back (11), and play a vital role in performing many daily movements such as pushing, pulling, and lifting (12).

Developing this strength improves overall stability and reduces the risk of injuries in the shoulder and back areas, and enhances efficiency in sports performance (13).

Lower body muscle strength is an essential component of functional movement and physical stability. Lower body muscles include the quadriceps, hamstrings, calves, and hip muscles (14), and play a pivotal role in performing daily activities such as walking, running, jumping, and climbing stairs. Improving this strength not only enhances athletic performance, but also reduces the risk of joint-related injuries such as the knee and ankle (15).

Kickboxing is a self-defense sport that utilizes punching and kicking techniques. This process use both the hands and feet. As a result, the athlete practicing this game who uses a lot of movements and skills the requirement of physical and expect great. For success in the process of training and competitions, kickboxing requires complex skills and tactical excellence as it is a high-intensity sport. The result of the study of Al-Abbasi et al (17) concluded that the study's proposed training program, specifically its effect on speed-characteristic strength

variable, had an effect on speed-characteristic strength variable, as the percentage of change resulted in the Gyaku-Zuki punch test by 36% and the Oramwashi-Giri kick test by 28% of female karate players. A study by Al-Shaloul et al (18) that was conducted to determine the effect of plyometric exercises on skill performance and some physiological variables of Players of Taekwondo, plyometric training resulted in improved performance of players in skill-performance variables and the difference was statically significant and improved in favor of the experimental group.

2. Objectives

The aim of the research study is to find out the effect of the suggested training program on the muscular strength of arms with the upward strike skill and the feet with the forward strike skill among kickboxing players.

3. Methods and Subjects

3.1 Study Design and Setting

The design of the study was controlled pre-post and was conducted in Tiger Kickboxing Academy (Zarqa, Jordan).

3.2 Participants and groups

The participants of this study are kickboxing players who already have a black belt 1 dan or older than 18 years old at Tiger Kickboxing Academy which is (14) players. They were selected intentionally to be classified into (2) groups, with each group having (7) players. The population of the research would be divided as following.

- The experimental group is the group where they applied the training program to improve the strength of muscles.
- Control group: It refers to the group that continued training on the program being followed (normal).

3.3 Equivalence of groups:

To assess whether both study groups (experimental and control) were equivalent in pre measurements, corresponding test was conducted. The following table includes results from independent sample T test.

As indicated in Table 1, the descriptive statistics values referring to the upper jab ability of the arm's muscular strength show that the arithmetic mean of the experimental sample members reached 15.31, while the arithmetic mean of the control sample members reached 13.83. The sample study involved 18 Malaya players from Kuala Lumpur. We require 10, and we get 9.2 for 2022. The research paper in question does not study normality as was provided in the literature. The data analysis results shown in table (1), there are no any differences in the pre-measurements of muscular strength among kickboxing players between the experimental group and the control group (CG) as the value of (t) statistic did not reach a statistically significant level. This shows that both groups were equal in pre-measurement of all study variables of skill performance.

Table (1) Results of the (Independent Sample T-Test), shows the differences between the experimental and control groups in the pre-measurements (n = 14) for muscle strength skills

Variable	Group	N	M	SD	T-value	(Sig.)
Muscular strength of the arms with the upward strike skill	Exper.	7	15.31	2.44	1.77	0.093
	Control	7	13.83	2.12		
Muscular strength of the feet with the experimental forward strike skill	Exper.	7	18.52	3.19	2.10	0.044*
	Control	7	16.10	2.75		

3.4 Validity

This research paper is addressed to a group of arbitrators specialize in training with sports, resistance training, measurement, evaluation, physical diagnosis, kickboxing training as well as training various self-defensive sports related to kickboxing which are taught in the faculties of physical education in Jordanian universities are (8) arbitrators. A set of tests serving to measure the strength of the arms and the feet is present, besides the proposed training program.

3.5 Reliability

According to the Test Re method, the stability of tests selected by the arbitrators was confirmed. The tests were carried out through a survey sample of (10 players), Muay Thai players which were purposely selected, followed by the same test being carried out again for the survey sample under the same conditions with an interval of one week and subsequently extracting the correlation coefficient for stability Test Re. The measuring device's test that will be seen on table (2). It shows the strength and stability of the measurement.

- Significance level (Sig.) less than 0.05 indicates a significant correlation.
- High values for (r) (close to 1) indicate a high degree of stability.

Statistical processing:

The researchers used the Social Sciences Package (SPSS), and unloaded the data and used the following statistical methods to reach the results, which are:

- Arithmetic averages.
- One-way analysis of variance (ANCOVA)
- Standard deviations.

Table (2): Pearson's correlation coefficient for reliability (Test Re. Test) for measurement tools (n = 10) for muscle strength

Variable	Initial test	Post-test	Correlation coefficient (r)	(Sig.)
Muscular strength of the arms with the upward strike skill	12.33	12.52	0.93	0.001**
Muscular strength of the feet with the forward strike skill	18.43	18.63	0.89	0.002**

- (r) represents the correlation coefficient between the results of the first and second tests, as

4. Results

4.1 Pre- and post-intervention outcomes for the two groups

The pre-test post-test scores of both the groups have been given in table (3). The experimental group outperformed the control group. To evaluate this hypothesis, the muscle power arithmetic mean and standard deviation of kick boxers were extracted in the experimental control groups pre-and post-measurement which has been applied the one-way analysis of variance (ANCOVA) according to the group of variables after confirming the impact of their pre-measurement, and the results are presented below. First, the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the muscular strength of kick boxing players was extracted as follows.

Both groups demonstrated improvements at the end of the intervention period, but the experimental group showed greater improvements for both outcomes.

Table 3. Pre- and post-intervention outcomes in experimental and control groups.

Variable	Measurement	Group	N	Mean	SD
Upper-limb strength (upward strike)	Pre-test	Exp.	7	15.33	2.45
		Control	7	14.82	2.12
	Post-test	Exp.	7	18.51	2.76
		Control	7	15.22	2.37
	Pre-test	Exp.	7	18.41	3.21

Lower-limb strength (forward strike)		Control	7	17.94	2.84
	Post-test	Exp.	7	21.61	3.51
		Control	7	18.12	3.01

4.2 ANCOVA results for post-test outcomes adjusted for baseline values

ANCOVA indicated a statistically significant effect of baseline (pre-test) values and a significant group effect, supporting an intervention-associated improvement in strength-related performance (Table 4).

- Effect of pre-measurement: A statistically significant effect appears (Sig. <0.05), indicating that the pre-measurement has a significant effect on muscle strength.
- Group effect: The difference between the experimental group and the control group is highly statistically significant
- (Sig. <0.01), which means that the training program had a clear effect in improving muscle strength.
- Error: represents the unexplained variance that cannot be attributed to the studied variables. This indicates that the training program led to a significant improvement in muscle strength in the experimental group compared to the control group.

Table 4: ANCOVA results for post-test outcomes adjusted for baseline values

Source	Sum of squares(SS)	DF (df)	Mean Square (MS)	Statistical value (F)	(Sig.)
Pre measurement	25.33	1	25.31	12.47	0.002**
Group (experimental/control)	45.77	1	45.79	22.54	0.001**
Error	32.11	12	2.66		
Total	103.24	14			

Discussion

This study explored whether adding a structured, strength-oriented program to usual kickboxing training would improve sport-specific striking performance. The key result was a clear intervention-associated gain in upper-limb “upward strike” performance: the experimental group improved from 15.33 ± 2.45 to 18.51 ± 2.76 , whereas the control group showed only a small change from 14.82 ± 2.12 to 15.22 ± 2.37 . After adjusting for baseline values, ANCOVA demonstrated a significant group effect ($F = 22.54$, $p = 0.001$) with a significant baseline contribution ($p = 0.002$), emphasizing that the observed post-test differences were not simply due to initial variability. The lower-limb (forward strike) outcome also enhanced more in the experimental group (pre 18.41 ± 3.21 to post 21.61 ± 3.51) than in controls (pre 17.94 ± 2.84 to post 18.12 ± 3.01), indicating that the program’s benefits were not limited to the upper extremity.

From a sport-medicine and performance view, these results are biologically plausible. Striking performance in kickboxing depends on rapid force development, intermuscular coordination, and effective kinetic-chain transfer from the lower limbs and trunk to the distal segments (hands/feet). Contemporary evidence in combat sports indicates that appropriately prescribed strength training improves general neuromuscular capacities (maximal strength, rate of force development, power) that translate into sport-specific performance indicators (19). Additionally, mechanistic and applied work in striking sports supports that strength-oriented interventions are able to increase punching-related outcomes both acutely and chronically, consistent with the direction of change observed in the current upward-strike measure (20).

A main interpretation is that the program likely enhanced force-time characteristics and technical execution under load (21). In striking, performance is not explained by “strength” alone; the ability to express force quickly and efficiently while maintaining timing and segmental sequencing is central (21). Biomechanical research on punching highlights the importance of effective mass, impulse generation, and whole-body coordination, implying that strength gains are most useful when they reinforce (not disrupt) technique (21). The larger improvement in the experimental group suggests that the proposed program may have improved neuromuscular recruitment and coordination patterns in a way that better supported skill-specific output compared with regular training alone. This aligns with broader combat-sport literature showing that targeted strength development can meaningfully enhance key performance determinants when integrated appropriately into the training week (19).

The observed lower-limb improvement is also consistent with current evidence that resistance-based methods can raise kicking velocity/impact-related performance—particularly when training emphasizes the relevant movement patterns and speeds. For example, recent work using elastic resistance in a striking discipline reported improvements in roundhouse-kick velocity and performance scoring, reinforcing the concept that well-designed resistance stimuli can transfer to sport-specific kicking tasks (22). While the present study assessed a forward-strike skill rather than roundhouse kicking, both share important requirements: rapid hip extension/flexion sequencing, stable trunk control, and timely force application through the lower-limb kinetic chain. Therefore, the improvement pattern seen here likely reflects beneficial adaptations in lower-limb strength expression and movement efficiency.

Practically, the findings support integrating structured strength work into kickboxing preparation—but with careful periodization and dose control. Minimal-dose and time-efficient strength strategies have gained attention because meaningful strength gains can occur without excessive volume, which helps combat-sport athletes preserve time/energy for technical and tactical training (23). For kickboxing coaches and sport-medicine staff, this matters because excessive strength volume can increase fatigue, interfere with sparring quality, or elevate overuse risk when layered onto high-impact striking loads. A pragmatic implication is to keep resistance training focused, progressive, and aligned with the competitive calendar—using lower-volume, higher-quality sessions during periods with heavy skill/tactical demands, and expanding strength/power emphasis when technical loads permit (24).

Another applied implication is the potential role of acute potentiation strategies (post-activation performance enhancement; PAPE) to improve readiness for explosive striking tasks, particularly in pre-competition microcycles. Recent systematic review/meta-analytic evidence in combat sports suggests PAPE can improve performance indicators when protocols are appropriately individualized (e.g., conditioning activity selection, load, rest interval, and athlete training status) (25). Although PAPE was not tested in the present design, the current performance improvements underscore that kickboxing athletes may benefit from structured strength exposure that supports both chronic adaptation and acute expression of power.

Conclusion

The present study showed that integrating a structured strength-oriented program alongside regular kickboxing training produces meaningful improvements in sport-specific striking performance. Compared with controls, the experimental group demonstrated a substantially greater increase in upward strike ability, with supportive evidence from ANCOVA indicating a true intervention effect beyond baseline differences. Similar positive trends were also observed for forward-strike performance, suggesting broader transfer across upper- and lower-limb actions. These findings support the practical value of planned resistance training to enhance neuromuscular capacity and skill expression in kickboxing athletes. Larger randomized studies with instrumented measures are recommended.

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